

Examining the impact of zinc in combination with organic manures on the yield and growth characteristics of chilli

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Abstract

Chilli (*Capsicum annuum L.*) is a vegetable, spice cum cash crop belong to the family of Solanaceae. It is called as the universal spice of India and originated from South America. It has a significant role in agricultural economics of the nation. A field experiment was conducted in a farmer's field located in Kaveripattinam village of the Mudukulathur block, Ramanathapuram district to evaluate the response of chilli to foliar and soil application of zinc combination with organic manures on the growth and yield attributes and yield of chilli fruits in zinc deficient soil. The soil was categorized as Fine, mixed isohyperthermic Vertic Haplustept, and low N, medium P and high K content, in a randomized block design with twelve treatments and three replications. The results revealed that the application of ZnSO₄ @ 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 188 kg vermicompost along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis registered maximum plant height at all three stages (45 DAT, 90 DAT and harvest) of crop growth (37.4, 60.4 and 100.0 cm), number of branches plant⁻¹ (3.8, 24.3 and 33.3) and chilli fruit yield (133.9 q ha⁻¹). This was followed by treatment application of ZnSO₄ @ 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 375 kg FYM along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis and the lowest treatment receiving the recommended dose of N, P₂O₅ and K₂O alone (120:60:30 kg ha⁻¹). It was revealed that natural chelated fertilizer prepared from ZnSO₄ incubated with organic manures for 30 days significantly improved the growth and yield of chilli.

Keywords: Chilli; *Capsicum annum L.*; Zinc; vermicompost; yield;

Introduction

Chilli (*Capsicum annuum L.*) is a remunerative vegetable, spice cum cash crop belong to the family of Solanaceae. It is called as the universal spice of India and originates from South America. India is the largest area (7.81 lakh ha) cultivating and producing (41.6 lakh tonnes) chilli and ranks first globally but 38th position in productivity (2312 kg ha⁻¹). In Tamil Nadu,

the total cultivated area under chilli was 0.46 lakh ha with a production of 0.21 lakh tonnes and the productivity of 410 kg ha⁻¹ (India stat, 2020). In Tamil Nadu major area under chilli cultivation is at Ramanathapuram (22441 ha) followed by Thoothukudi, Sivagangai, Virudhunagar, Thirunelveli and Ariyalur districts. Despite a larger area being used for chilli cultivation, the yield and profitability of chilli are declining because of poor management. In terms of chilli production, Indian soils produce a significantly lower yield, which may be the result of improper fertilization and deficiencies of micronutrients (Bose and Tripathi, 1996). One of the problems faced by chilli growing farmers is flower, fruit drop and zinc deficiency which drastically reduces the yield. Zinc play a vital role in the growth and productivity of different vegetable crops including chilli (Shil *et. al.*, 2013). Zinc involved in the biosynthesis of auxin (Indole-3-acetic acid) and it is also the metabolic activator of many cellular enzymes in plants. The information of the role of Zn on morphological, physiological and biochemical traits in chilli is meagre. Hence it is important to study the influence of Zn on morpho-physiological and yield components in chilli to boost the productivity potential. Application of organic manures in crop production is in vogue for several years. Addition of well decomposed FYM not only supply plant nutrients but also acts as a binding material and improves the soil physical properties. Beneficial effects of earthworms and their cast were known as early as in Darwin's era. But the potential of vermicompost to supply nutrients and to support beneficial microbes has been recognized recently. Organics alone do not produce spectacular increase in crop yields due to their low nutrient status. Therefore, to maintain soil productivity on a sustainable basis, blending of organic and inorganic sources of nutrients needs to be adopted. Particularly chilli needs heavy manuring for better growth and high yield. Use of judicious combinations of organic and inorganic fertilizer sources are essential not only to maintain the soil health but also sustain productivity (Malewar *et al.*, 1998). Keeping these points in view, the present study was conducted to evaluate the effect of zinc sulphate alone and incubation with various organic manures on the growth, yield attributes and chilli fruit production in Zn deficient soils of Ramanathapuram district, Tamil Nadu.

Materials and Methods

Experimental site: The field experiment was carried out to understand the response of Zn to the growth and yield of chilli in a farmer field located in Kaveripattinam village of the Mudukulathur block, Ramanathapuram district, Tamil Nadu, during the *kharif* season from 28th September 2021 to 15th March 2022. The mean annual temperature and mean annual rainfall in the Ramanathapuram district was 29.1°C and 770 mm respectively.

Enrichment of organics fortified with Zn: The organic sources employed in the incubation of Zn are vermicompost and farmyard manure. The enrichment process included ZnSO₄ @ 25 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 250 kg FYM for 30 days (1:10 ratio), ZnSO₄ @ 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 125 kg FYM for 30 days (1:10 ratio), ZnSO₄ @ 25 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 125 kg Vermicompost for 30 days (1:5 ratio), ZnSO₄ @ 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 188 kg Vermicompost for 30 days (1:5 ratio).

Experimental details: The field experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with twelve treatments and three replication 20 m² (5 m X 4 m). The details of the treatments are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Treatment details of the experiment

T ₁	N, P ₂ O ₅ , K ₂ O @ 120:60:30 kg ha ⁻¹
T ₂	N, P ₂ O ₅ , K ₂ O on STCR basis
T ₃	T ₂ + Basal application of ZnSO ₄ @ 25 kg ha ⁻¹
T ₄	T ₂ + Basal application of ZnSO ₄ @ 37.5 kg ha ⁻¹
T ₅	T ₂ + ZnSO ₄ @ 25 kg ha ⁻¹ incubated with 250 kg FYM for 30 days (1:10 ratio)
T ₆	T ₂ + ZnSO ₄ @ 37.5 kg ha ⁻¹ incubated with 125 kg FYM for 30 days (1:10 ratio)
T ₇	T ₂ + ZnSO ₄ @ 25 kg ha ⁻¹ incubated with 125 kg Vermicompost for 30 days (1:5 ratio)
T ₈	T ₂ + ZnSO ₄ @ 37.5 kg ha ⁻¹ incubated with 188 kg Vermicompost for 30 days (1:5 ratio)
T ₉	T ₂ + Foliar application of ZnSO ₄ @ 0.5 % on 20, 40, 60 DAT
T ₁₀	T ₃ + Foliar application of ZnSO ₄ @ 0.5 % on 20, 40, 60 DAT
T ₁₁	T ₂ + Basal application of ZnEDTA @ 2 kg ha ⁻¹
T ₁₂	T ₂ + Foliar application of ZnEDTA @ 0.5 % on 20, 40, 60 DAT

Data Collection and Analysis

Before the experimentation, soil samples were collected at randomly at 0-30 cm depth across the experimental site and made in a single composite. The composite soil sample was processed and used for the analysis of physico-chemical characteristics viz., soil reaction (pH)(Potentiometry, Jackson, 1973), electrical conductivity (EC) (Conductometry, Jackson, 1973), soil organic carbon (Dichromate wet digestion method, Walkley and black, 1934), available nitrogen (Alkaline permanganate method, Subbaiah and Asija, 1956), available phosphorus (Olsen method, Olsen et al., 1954), available potassium (neutral normal NH₄OAc

method, Stanford and English, 1949), DTPA extractable Zn, Fe, Cu, Mn (Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer, Lindsay and Norvell, 1978). From each plot, five plants were selected randomly and tagged and the following growth and yield parameters were observed. Plant height was measured from the ground level to the tip of the terminal bud and expressed in cm. The number of branches per plant was counted from the selected tagged plants and the mean number of fruits, was determined and expressed in numbers. The yield data were collected at physiological maturity and after the crop was harvested. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to examine the growth and yield (kg ha^{-1}) obtained in the research, as recommended by Panse and Sukhatme (1967).

Results and Discussion

The present study showed that chilli (*Capsicum annum* L.), samba variety, the plant growth and yield attributes were highly influenced by the soil application of Zn and enriched organics along with STCR based N, P_2O_5 and K_2O .

Initial properties: The data of various physico-chemical properties of the initial soil are presented in Table 2. The soil texture was sandy clay in nature with a bulk density (1.18 Mg m^{-3}) and particle density (2.45 Mg m^{-3}). The pH of the experimental soil was moderately alkaline (8.32). The soil was low in alkaline $\text{Alk.KMnO}_4 - \text{N}$ (200.5 kg ha^{-1}), medium in Olsen's- P (13.7 kg ha^{-1}), high in $\text{NH}_4\text{OAc}- \text{K}$ (362 kg ha^{-1}), low in organic carbon content (3.7 g kg^{-1}) and CEC of $26.2 \text{ c mol (p}^+) \text{ kg}^{-1}$. The total nutrient status of the soil was 0.075, 0.031 and 0.420 per cent of N, P and K respectively. The exchangeable calcium and magnesium were 7.21 and $8.32 \text{ c mol (p}^+) \text{ kg}^{-1}$ respectively. The DTPA extractable Zn was found to be deficient (0.63 mg kg^{-1}). The soil was categorized as “Fine, mixed isohyperthermic *Vertic Haplustept*” by the United State Department of Agriculture (USDA) soil taxonomy.

Table 2. Initial soil parameters of the experimental site

Particulars		Vertic Haplustept (Kadaladi)
A.	Mechanical composition	
	Clay (%)	31.30
	Silt (%)	7.8
	Fine Sand (%)	31.50
	Coarse Sand (%)	28.40
	Textural class	Sandy clay
B.	Physical Properties	
	Bulk density (Mg m^{-3})	1.18
	Particle density (Mg m^{-3})	2.45

	Porosity (%)	45.43
C.	Physico-chemical properties	
	pH	8.32
	EC (dSm ⁻¹)	0.40
	AEC (c mol (p+) kg ⁻¹)	2.80
	CEC (c mol (p+) kg ⁻¹)	26.2
D.	Chemical properties	
	Free CaCO ₃ (%)	6.73
	Sesquioxide (%)	6.45
	Total nitrogen (%)	0.075
	Total phosphorus (%)	0.031
	Total potassium (%)	0.420
	Organic carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	3.7
	Alk- KMnO ₄ –nitrogen (kg ha ⁻¹)	200.5
	Olsen – phosphorus (kg ha ⁻¹)	13.7
	NH ₄ OAc - potassium (kg ha ⁻¹)	362
	Exchangeable calcium (c mol (p+) kg ⁻¹)	7.21
	Exchangeable magnesium (c mol (p+) kg ⁻¹)	8.32
	CaCl ₂ -S (mg kg ⁻¹)	8.7
	Available iron (mg kg ⁻¹)	10.8
	Available manganese (mg kg ⁻¹)	11.6
	Available zinc (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.63
	Available copper (mg kg ⁻¹)	1.89

Effect of Zn and fortified organic manures on growth attributes : The application of Zn significantly influenced the growth attributes of chilli, as shown in Table 3. The plant height, number of branches were significantly (P = 0.05) higher in the treatment receiving ZnSO₄ @ 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 188 kg vermicompost along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis than in the other treatments. Thus, this result might be due to the increased availability of Zn for chilli during the critical stages, as Zn starvation greatly reduces the growth and development of chilli.

Table 3. Effect of zinc fertilization on plant height (cm) and number of branches at various growth stages of chilli

Treatment	Plant height (cm)			Number of branches		
	45 DAT	90 DAT	At harvest	45 DAT	90 DAT	At harvest
T1	26.8	46.0	78.8	1.8	11.1	20.1
T2	28.4	47.8	81.0	2.2	12.9	21.9
T3	30.5	51.1	86.9	2.8	16.0	25.0

T4	33.2	54.4	91.4	3.1	18.6	27.6
T5	34.5	56.4	94.2	3.2	20.8	29.8
T6	36.6	59.3	97.4	3.7	22.9	31.9
T7	35.0	57.3	95.1	3.4	21.9	30.9
T8	37.4	60.4	100.0	3.8	24.3	33.3
T9	29.4	49.3	83.7	2.6	13.7	22.7
T10	32.1	52.9	89.1	3.0	17.4	26.4
T11	34.0	55.6	93.1	3.6	19.4	28.4
T12	30.1	50.3	85.3	2.7	15.2	24.2
Mean	32.3	53.4	89.7	3.0	17.9	26.9
SEd	0.71	0.94	1.71	0.11	0.45	0.45
CD (P = 0.05)	1.48	1.96	3.55	0.23	0.94	0.94

Plant height: The application of vermicompost incubated with zinc sulphate exhibited favourable results on plant height. Among the various treatments, application of 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ ZnSO₄ incubated with 188 kg of vermicompost along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis (T₈) was significantly superior on improving the plant height by recording 37.4, 60.4 and 100.0 cm followed by T₆ (ZnSO₄ @ 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 375 kg FYM along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis). The treatment T₈ was statistically on par with T₆ which was applied with ZnSO₄ @ 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 375 kg FYM along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis. The lowest plant height of 26.8, 46.0 and 78.8 cm at 45, 90 DAT and at harvest stages respectively were recorded in the treatment receiving RDF alone (120: 60: 30 kg ha⁻¹). In experimental field investigation, enriched ZnSO₄ outperformed the control in terms of boosting growth metrics such as plant height, with 39.5 % during 45 DAT, 31.3 % during 90 DAT and 26.9 % at harvest. An increase in plant height due to the application of Zn irrespective of its levels were observed. This may be attributed to the enhanced photosynthetic and other metabolic activity which leads to an increase in various plant metabolites responsible for cell division and elongation as opined by Hatwar *et al.* (2003) which leads to produced the tallest plant. Ghosh *et al.* (2020) reported that increased plant height obtained from application of zinc may be due to role of Zn in auxin biosynthesis, which plays important role in apical dominance of plants.

Number of branches per plant: The number of branches per plant was also enhanced by the application of Zn with vermicompost. The treatment 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ ZnSO₄ incubated with 188 kg vermicompost along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis (T₈) registered the maximum number of branches per plant at all the stages of crop growth (3.8, 24.3 and 33.3) followed by

the treatment receiving $37.5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ incubated with 375 kg FYM along with N, P_2O_5 and K_2O on STCR basis (T_6). The lowest number of branches per plant (1.8, 11.1 and 20.1) was registered in the treatment receiving RDF alone ($120: 60: 30 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$). This might be due to the increased nutrient supply with the addition of fertilizer along with organic manures. Angami *et al.* (2017) also reported increase in number of branches of chilli by application of Zinc (ZnSO_4). It may be ascribed due to sufficient availability of zinc to plant which might have enhanced catalytic or stimulatory effect on most of the physiological and metabolic processes of plant. It also helps in enhances the absorption of essential elements via increasing the cation exchange capacity of roots, plant root formation, carbohydrate metabolism, protein synthesis and growth promoters activations which ultimately produces healthy plant with the maximum productive branches of the crop. Zn was found to increase the photosynthetic activity and the rate of respiration which results in improved the growth (Martin *et al.*, 1966). These present findings also are in conformity with earlier workers of Abbasi *et al.* (2010), Elayaraja and Dhanasekaran (2016). The control treatment (RDF alone) recorded the lowest growth characters viz., plant height, number of branches per plant compared to other treatments. Similar results obtained with earlier workers Elayaraja and Dhanasekaran (2016).

Effect of Zn and fortified organic manures on yield attribute: Incubation of Zn with vermicompost showed a significant ($P = 0.05$) impact on the number of fruits plant⁻¹, fruit length, single fruit weight and 100 seed weight. Among the various treatments, the combined application of $\text{ZnSO}_4 @ 37.5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ incubated with 375 kg FYM along with N, P_2O_5 and K_2O on STCR basis was found to be effective in increasing the number of fruits plant⁻¹ (82.6), fruit length (9.10 cm), single fruit weight (5.10 g) and 100 seed weight plant⁻¹ (0.60 g), followed by the treatment receiving $37.5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ incubated with 375 kg FYM along with N, P_2O_5 and K_2O on STCR basis (T_6) with 79.5 fruits per plant, 8.87 cm of fruit length, 4.83 g of single fruit weight and 0.60 g of 100 seed weight plant⁻¹. The lowest number of fruits plant⁻¹ (51.6), fruit length (6.17 cm), single fruit weight (3.10 g) and 100 seed weight plant⁻¹ (0.52 g) were recorded in the RDF treatment (T_1). This might be due to the improved production of phyto-hormones prompted by Zn fertilization, which in turn increased the fruit development and production (Elizabeth *et al.*, 2017). The most important effect of including Zn applications to chilli is that it can improve yield and yield components and growth characteristics (Hatwar *et al.*, 2003) as its application increases endogenous hormones like auxins, gibberellins, and melatonin which

will benefit growth, development and fruit production (Zhu *et al.*, 2020). Followed by it, fruit length the treatment received with 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ of ZnSO₄ incubated with 188 kg vermicompost along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis was found to have highest fruit length and lowest fruit length obtained in the treatment receiving RDF. This might be due to more accumulation of photosynthesis was probably due to more vigor, growth (Iyenger and Raja, 1998) and significantly enhance both the size and number of cells in plant (Natesh *et al.*, 2005).

The increment in fruit weight must be due to the timely application of Zn as it plays a vital role in accumulation of other nutrients including N, P, K and Ca. zinc application boosts chilli weight because of increasing cells and cell division and work in the volume of intercellular space in mesocarpic cells in addition to rapid metabolite translocation and sink fruits (Brahmachari and Rani, 2001) and also aid in the preparation of tryptophan, which is an amino acid that aids in the manufacture of proteins, as well as auxins, which are plant growth regulators that result in improved fruit growth (Wojcik and Wojcik, 2003). Followed by it, the increment in 100 seed weight also followed the same trend with the application of 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ of ZnSO₄ incubated with 188 kg vermicompost along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis was registering the highest 100 seed weight compared to other treatments. Naga *et al.*, (2013) reported that application of micro nutrient mixture in tomato increase 100 seed weight as compared to the control. The similar findings with the application of zinc have also been recorded by Dongr *et al.* 2000 in vary vegetable crops those various concentrations of zinc treatments significantly influenced the 1000 seed weight of lentil.

Effect of Zn and fortified organic manures on chilli fruit yield: Chilli fruit yield is a direct correlation between growth and development of various morphological components. The data defined in table revealed that application of ZnSO₄ @ 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 188 kg vermicompost along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis delivered the highest chilli fruit yield (133.9 q ha⁻¹) followed by T₆ - ZnSO₄ @ 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 375 kg FYM along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis (127 q ha⁻¹) and it was statistically on par with T₇ - ZnSO₄ @ 25 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 125 kg vermicompost along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis (125.1 q ha⁻¹). Treatment T₁ - RDF (N:P₂O₅:K₂O @ 120:60:30 kg ha⁻¹) had the lowest chilli fruit yield (90 q ha⁻¹). While Behera and Chitdeshwari (2021) also supported these findings that highest fruit per plant recorded in the treatment soil test based NPK+ 37.5 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹. This might be due to the improved production of phyto-hormones prompted by Zn fertilization, which in turn increased the fruit development and production (Elizabeth *et al.*, 2017). The most important effect of including Zn applications to chilli is that it can improve yield and yield components and growth characteristics (Hatwar *et al.*, 2003) as its application increases endogenous hormones like auxins,

gibberellins, and melatonin which will benefit growth, development and fruit production (Zhu *et al.*, 2020). This result is also similar to Ali *et al.*, (2008) reported that the effect of zinc which is essential for the carbonic enzyme and photosynthesis, resulting in increase in translocation of photosynthesis in fruits and decrease in flowers and fruits abscission (Graham *et al.*, 2000). The zinc increases the number of fruits per plant by increasing IAA synthesis (Shnain *et al.*, 2014) as well as carbonhydrates translocation (Singh and Tawari, 2013).

Table 4. Effect of zinc fertilization on yield parameters of chilli at harvest stage

Treatment	Yield attributes			
	No. of fruits plant ⁻¹	Fruit length (cm)	Single fruit weight (g)	100 seed weight plant ⁻¹ (g)
T1	51.6	6.17	3.10	0.52
T2	54.3	6.37	3.30	0.53
T3	63.3	7.37	3.37	0.55
T4	68.9	7.83	3.53	0.56
T5	74.5	8.47	4.57	0.58
T6	79.5	8.87	4.83	0.59
T7	77.8	8.67	4.63	0.59
T8	82.6	9.10	5.10	0.60
T9	57.2	6.70	3.37	0.54
T10	66.7	7.53	3.80	0.56
T11	72.4	8.13	4.33	0.57
T12	60.5	7.00	3.53	0.55
Mean	67.4	7.68	3.96	0.56
SEd	1.791	0.171	0.121	0.009
CD (P = 0.05)	3.715	0.355	0.252	0.020

Table 5. Effect of zinc fertilization on yield of chilli fruit at harvest stage

S.No	Treatment	Fruit yield (q ha ⁻¹)
1	T ₁ - RDF (N:P ₂ O ₅ :K ₂ O @ 120:60:30 kg ha ⁻¹)	90.0 ^k
2	T ₂ - N, P ₂ O ₅ and K ₂ O on STCR basis	96.9 ^j
3	T ₃ - T ₂ + Basal application of ZnSO ₄ @ 25 kg ha ⁻¹	109.7 ^{gh}
4	T ₄ - T ₂ + Basal application of ZnSO ₄ @ 37.5 kg ha ⁻¹	115.8 ^{ef}
5	T ₅ - T ₂ + ZnSO ₄ @ 25 kg incubated with 250 kg FYM for 30 days (1:10 ratio)	121.6 ^{cd}

6	T ₆ - T ₂ + ZnSO ₄ @ 37.5 kg incubated with 375 kg FYM for 30 days (1:10 ratio)	127.0 ^b
7	T ₇ - T ₂ + ZnSO ₄ @ 25 kg incubated with 125 kg VC for 30 days (1:5 ratio)	125.1 ^{bc}
8	T ₈ - T ₂ + ZnSO ₄ @ 37.5 kg incubated with 188 kg VC for 30 days (1:5 ratio)	133.9 ^a
9	T ₉ - T ₂ + Foliar spray of ZnSO ₄ @ 0.5% three times	102.8 ⁱ
10	T ₁₀ - T ₃ + Foliar spray of ZnSO ₄ @ 0.5% three times	112.5 ^{fg}
11	T ₁₁ - T ₂ + Basal application of Zn EDTA @ 2 kg ha ⁻¹	119.4 ^{de}
12	T ₁₂ - T ₂ + Foliar spray of Zn EDTA @ 0.5% three times	107.6 ^h
	CD	4.64
	SEd	2.24

Conclusion

The application of Zn in conjunction with organic manures significantly ($p = 0.05$) increased growth and yield parameters in chilli. The results concluded that soil application of ZnSO₄ @ 37.5 kg ha⁻¹ incubated with 188 kg vermicompost along with N, P₂O₅ and K₂O on STCR basis significantly increased the growth and yield of chilli in Zn deficient soils. Thus, the application of ZnSO₄ along with organic manures is recommended for better crop growth and yield of chilli.

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